

JavaScript Online Clone Patterns

Analysis Study: Artifacts

javascript-corpus: It has all syntactically validated Stack Overflow extracted snippets in method level granularity. The 292 downloaded and filtered GitHub repositories files are also provided with the complete statistics.

online-clone-pairs: It contains Siamese-generated clone raw search results. The 12579 reported clone pair list also included the top 10% (1257) manually classified clone pairs in different patterns.

scripts: It contains all the source code and scripts that were created and utilized in the Replication Study. It contains three types of packages: python, javaScript, and shell.

- The python package contains the scripts for downloading, extracting, and analyzing the Stack Overflow data dump.
- The javaScript package contains the script for validating Stack Overflow and GitHub snippets with ESLint, Espree, and JSHint.
- Furthermore, the shell package contains unix bash scripts that help to remove duplicate files , remove unnecessary directories, compute LOC

siamese-javascript-extended-jars: It contains the extended version of Siamese that supports JavaScript clone search. The **config.properties** file includes the configuration parameters we followed during the clone searching.